

Exploring the Key Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of First Year Students at Undergraduate Level

Abstract: Since the number of students entering into the higher education system is increasing along with the dropout rates, therefore it is important for the institutions to identify the reasons that impact students' academic performance in order to introduce the provision for necessary support for the students. This study is stimulated by the demand to determine such factors at undergraduate level that cause academic failure and dropout rates. Therefore, this study attempts to investigate what students see as the main influential factor the effects the academic performance of first year undergraduate students at university level. A quantitative research approach was followed to conduct the study. A survey was designed with questionnaires and was administered. Total 450 first year students, both from public and private universities in Bangladesh, were selected by convenience and stratified simple random sampling. The findings of this study disclosed the consistency with previous research conducted on student academic performance. According to the research findings appropriate choice of course of study; students' interest in the subject; regular attendance at lectures; timely and regular examination preparation; teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills; efficacious written communications skills; effective study methods are the topmost success factors that influence students' academic performance. Oppositely, absence of interest in the course content; inadequate or poor exam preparation; irregular attendance at class lectures/tutorials; late submission of assignments; lack of self-discipline, self-motivation and confidence; incapability to differentiate between important and unimportant information; heavy course workload; inefficient time management reverse the academic performance of the students.

Keywords: Influential Factors, Academic performance, Higher education in Bangladesh, Students' performance in first year, Success factors of academic performance, Failure factors of academic performance.

Introduction

In recent years, students' performance has received significant attention in the education literature. Students' academic performance is the key indicator of student achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically assess students' achievement by their classroom performance, graduation rates and results from standardized tests. Students' academic performance often defined students' cumulative grade point, test scores and persistence level (Finn & Rock, 1997). There are various methods of measuring students' academic performance in terms of success and or failure and this includes: Continuous Assessment (CA), Summative Assessment, Term Final Examination, Grade Point Average (GPA), Graduation rate etc. According to Rajandran et al. (2015), student performance is commonly perceived as the combined product of socio-economic, psychological and environmental factors. Hence, the factors are anticipated to differ from one country to another.

Transition from school life to university life is one of the biggest challenges the first-year university students as it presents new opportunities to the students. This transitional phase sometimes effects their academic and personal life. According to Fisher and Hood (1987), from the perspective of psychological aspects, the transition to university life requires the students

to bring changes to their previous routines and life style in order to regulate themselves to a new living and study setting which includes acclimatizing to new social and residential changes and challenges which may end up with consequences like increase in psychological disorder, unhappiness, obsession and absent-mindedness. The challenges for newcomer students to the university also derived from unlikely views about class sizes, lack of availability of teaching and non-teaching supportive staff, and unmanageable workload [cited in Hien Thu Thi Le et al., 2020]. Moreover, the newcomers may lack the fundamental understanding of course contents (Hien Thu Thi Le et al., 2020). In result, the academic performance of the students may face impediments in their early university study life.

Study skills is considered to be one of the most decisive and most consistent forecasters of academic performance by earlier research findings [cited in Hien Thu Thi Le et al., 2020]. Hassanbeigi et al. (2011) discussed that to get success at university level, students need to own few important skills like proper time management ability, critical and analytical ability, attentiveness and memorization skills; note-taking ability; anxiety and fear management; good organisational ability; motivation and attitude, and reading comprehension ability [cited in Hien Thu Thi Le et al. (2020)].

There is an implicit assumption that, students who got opportunity to take admission into a university education will be proficient enough to successfully complete the degree they have registered. Therefore, the students are left out with no other options except academic success. This huge pressure on the students to become successful may impact their academic performance at the very beginning of their academic journey at university level even though they have good academic records at high school level and university entrance examination. Killen (1994) suggested that although the careful and thoughtful construction of school certificate examinations or university admission examinations, it is not prospective to be considered as solid predictors of accomplishment at university level because those examination hardly measure non-intellective factors which are connected to success that students face after they enrol at university. Killen (1994) concluded that some of the most noteworthy features in defining students' academic success at university level included student's interest in the course or subject, self-motivation, self-discipline and determination which cannot be foreseen directly from school examination result or university entrance examination results.

There are plenty of evidences in the previously conducted research works on 'teaching and learning' to recommend that aspects such as instruction strategies, motivation of students, students' approach to study, collaboration between students and the academician, and the atmosphere of the educational institutions, cultural expectations, psychosocial factors and number of additional factors are expected to influence undergraduates' success at university level [cited in Fraser and Killen, 2003].

According to Schmelzer et al. (1987), perseverance and regular study was the greater shared reason by the college students for their academic achievement. Planning suitable goals, decent study atmosphere, and effective time management were the other significant reasons considered by the students. Lack of study habits, improper time management, and inadequate goal setting were attributed as factors to academic failure.

According to Olatunji et al. (2016), previous research works have recognized study habit, student's self-concept, instructor's qualification, instruction method, university environment and administration as factors influencing students' academic performance. In addition, the

home setting or environment of the students stands as a factor which exert great impact on students' accomplishments.

Considering the earlier study findings on influencing factors for students' academic achievements, this study which aims to explore the main factors that influence the academic performance of first-year students at undergraduate level in Bangladesh may provide a portrait to the university students, teachers, educators and administrators to understand and take necessary intervention to address this issue regards to academic performance as very few study have been conducted on this particular issue in Bangladesh. The results of this study may work as a document on student academic achievements, and may offer necessary guideline to those who are associated with higher education management system for intervening and decision making in concern to student academic performance.

Objective of the study

The objective of this study was to explore the key factors what students perceived as extremely influential for their academic accomplishment or let-down at the very early stage of their academic career at university level.

Research methodology

The methodology of the study is described through nature of the study, the sample and sampling design, instruments of data collection, and data analysis. These are spelled out in the following sections:

The study was quantitative in nature. In quantitative research, the investigator attempts to identify a research problem based on the trends in the arena or on the prerequisite to explain why something occurs (Creswell, 2012).

A questionnaire consisting of various success and failure factors was administered to collect information for the study. According to Lloyd et al. (2012) [cited in Sibanda et al. 2015], questionnaires are considered as a reliable tool for quantitative studies. The items of the questionnaire were adopted from the study of Killen's (1994) on the success/failure factors that influence academic achievements of the university students. This questionnaire was also used in previous studies by Fraser & Killen, (2003), (2005); Zhang & Aasheim (2011); Ndlovu, (2011); Sibanda et al. (2015). Apart from demographic information, the questionnaire consisted of fifty (50) statements describing academic success factors and fifty-three (53) statements describing academic failure factors. These factors related with success and failure were classified on a four-point Likert type questionnaire asking the respondents to rank each factor from the response options of NI = not influential, SI = slightly influential, FI = fairly influential, HI = highly influential.

One public university and one private university was chosen for the study following the convenience sampling technique. Only first year students, who have completed at least a semester were considered as a respondent for this study to accomplish the purpose. 450 students were selected by following stratified simple random sampling. Students were chosen from different academic disciplines.

In quantitative analysis, data are analysed using mathematical procedures, called statistics. These analyses consist of breaking down the data into parts to answer the research questions

(Creswell, 2012). In this study, data gathered from the questionnaire were analysed using simple descriptive methods along with appropriate regression analyses.

Findings of the study

The outcomes from the "success factor" and "failure factor" statement of the questionnaire are described first and then the overall discussion are made.

Success factor statement responses

Statements pertained to success factor for academic performance covered the range from 1 (Not Influential) to 4 (Highly Influential). The mean score with standard deviation of the replies given by respondents ranged from 3.79 for 'Appropriate choice of course of study' to 2.61 for 'Encouragement, motivation and support from peer'. Subsequently, Students' interest in the subject (mean 3.72); Regular attendance at lectures (mean 3.71); Timely and regular examination preparation (mean 3.68); Teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills (mean 3.63); Effective written communications skills (mean 3.59); Effective study methods (mean 3.57); Medium of study (English/Bangla) (mean 3.56); Teachers' professional knowledge and credentials (mean 3.52); Self-confidence (mean 3.49); Teachers who can inspire students' (mean 3.48); Tutorial support (mean 3.46); Self-motivation (mean 3.45); Self-discipline (mean 3.43); Regular study practice and Teacher student relationship (mean 3.41) are the topmost success factors that influence students' academic performance. (See table-1)

Failure factor statement responses

The items on failure factor also covered the range from 1 (Not Influential) to 4 (Highly Influential). The item that mostly contributed to student failure was 'Lack of interest in the course content' (mean 3.68). The item rated lowest which contributed to student failure was 'Part-time job by the students' (mean 2.32). Other uppermost failure factors influencing students' academic performance included: Inadequate or poor exam preparation (mean 3.62); Irregular attendance at lectures/tutorials (mean 3.62); Late submission of assignments (mean 3.54); Lack of self-discipline (mean 3.51); Lack of self-motivation (mean 3.49); Lack of confidence (mean 3.45); Incapability to differentiate between important and unimportant information (mean 3.45); Heavy course workload (mean 3.44); Inefficient time management (mean 3.42); Previous poor academic foundation (mean 3.41); Insufficient effort (e.g., study, exam prep) (mean 3.39); Personal or family crisis (mean 3.39); Financial problems (mean 3.35); Poor study techniques (mean 3.34) and so on. (See table-2)

Table-1. Mean scores of ‘success factor’ items from first-year students

Question Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
Appropriate choice of course of study	3.79	0.498
Students’ curiosity in the subject	3.72	0.491
Regular presence at class lectures	3.71	0.821
Timely and regular examination preparation	3.68	0.498
Teachers’ pedagogical knowledge and skills	3.63	0.749
Effective written communications skills	3.59	0.491
Effective study methods	3.57	0.633
Medium of study (English/Bangla)	3.56	0.401
Teachers’ professional knowledge and credentials	3.52	0.498
Self-confidence	3.49	0.495
Teachers who can inspire students’	3.48	0.398
Tutorial support	3.46	0.491
Self-motivation	3.45	0.489
Self-discipline	3.43	0.491
Regular study practice	3.41	0.401
Teacher student relationship	3.41	0.401
A balance between academic preference and social life	3.35	0.403
The desire to learn	3.34	0.749
Financial security	3.31	0.493
Consistent effort of the learners	3.27	0.749
Creative and critical thinking ability	3.24	1.021
Clear understanding of teachers’ expectation by the students’	3.23	0.491
Family support	3.22	0.401
Encouragement, motivation and support from teachers’	3.21	0.491
Satisfactory accommodation	3.19	0.401
A stable personal life	3.17	0.981
Linkage of the study subjects with career goal	3.14	0.406
Regular and comprehensive feedback by teachers’	3.13	0.801
General academic ability	2.99	0.491
Willingness to ask for help from peers	2.97	0.491
Regular use of the library	2.97	0.401
Hard work, commitment and dedication	2.96	0.633
Effective examination techniques	2.95	0.401
Support from peer group	2.93	0.491
Adaptability with University procedures and guidelines	2.91	0.401
Ability to work as a member of a group	2.89	0.491
Clear guideline with expected learning outcome	2.89	0.749
Ability to learn independently	2.89	0.301
Willingness to ask for help from teachers’	2.88	0.749
Encouragement, motivation and support from parents’	2.88	0.749
Availability of quality learning resources	2.82	0.765
Ability to manage stress	2.81	0.401
Implementation of theory into practice	2.81	0.633
Involvement in co-curricular activities	2.61	0.633
Access to university library and internet service	2.77	1.097
Positive influence of friends	2.96	0.301
Student's attitude towards learning	2.75	0.633
Continuous assessment	2.71	0.633
Willingness to accept academic challenge	2.66	0.633
Encouragement, motivation and support from peer	2.61	0.749

Table-2. Mean ratings on 'failure factor' items from first-year students

Question Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
Lack of curiosity in the course content	3.68	0.621
Inadequate or poor exam preparation	3.62	0.491
Irregular appearance at class lectures/tutorials	3.62	0.749
Late submission of assignments	3.54	0.491
Absence of self-discipline	3.51	0.498
Absence of self-motivation	3.49	0.495
Lack of confidence	3.45	0.49
Failure to differentiate between significant and insignificant information	3.45	0.633
Heavy course workload	3.44	0.633
Inefficient time management	3.42	0.401
Previous poor academic foundation	3.41	0.749
Insufficient effort (e.g., study, exam prep)	3.39	0.81
Personal or family crisis	3.39	0.638
Financial problems	3.35	0.451
Poor study techniques	3.34	0.398
Badly structured presentations by lecturers	3.33	0.491
Poor study skills of students	3.32	0.749
Boring presentations by lecturers	3.31	0.701
Unclear criteria and lecturers' expectations of assignments	3.29	0.401
Textbooks available in one language only	3.29	0.635
Inability to balance study and social commitments	3.27	0.491
Too much dependency on directions/guidance by teachers'	3.23	0.749
Teachers' lacking to understand the needs of students'	3.21	0.491
Inappropriate and biased assessment procedures by teachers	3.21	0.749
Lack of persistence	3.19	0.489
Low self esteem	3.13	0.921
Inability to cope with stress	3.13	0.491
Failure to approach lecturers/tutors for help	3.12	0.491
Lack of self-assessment	3.11	0.801
Lack of academic ability	2.99	0.401
Personal clash with the teachers	2.99	0.633
Lack of ability to bridge between theory and practice	2.96	0.491
Too many extra unnecessary interests	2.95	0.921
Poor examination techniques	2.94	0.491
Low input from lecturers to motivate the students	2.93	0.981
Poor language abilities of lecturers	2.92	0.401
Laziness or apathy	2.91	0.491
Misinterpretation of course requirements	2.91	0.749
Fear of failure	2.89	1.097
Too many preferences on students' time schedule	2.88	0.401
Incapability to practice higher order thinking skills	2.86	0.497
Failure to comprehend the depth of understanding required at tertial level	2.83	0.401
Deficiency in clear career goal setting	2.81	0.401
Inadequate university library facilities	2.81	0.459
Lack of communication between teacher and student	2.78	0.401
Absence of rewards for student efforts	2.77	0.821
Lack of maturity from the students'	2.65	0.633
Influence of Peer group	2.64	0.901
Teachers' unrealistic high expectations on students	2.62	0.401
Health and well being	2.61	0.301
Noisy classroom environment	2.56	0.749

Discussions

Findings from this study support the previous research findings and existed literature that appropriate choice of course of study; students' interest in the subject; consistent presence at lectures; timely and systematic examination preparation; teachers' pedagogical knowledge and skills; effective written communications skills; effective study methods; teachers' professional knowledge and credentials; self-confidence; self-motivation and self-discipline of student are the topmost key success factors academic performance. On the other hand, absence of interest in the course materials; inadequate or poor exam preparation; irregular appearance at class lectures/tutorials; late submission of assignments; lack of self-discipline, self-motivation and confidence; incapability to discriminate between important and unimportant material; heavy course workload; inefficient time management; previous poor academic foundation; insufficient study effort; personal or family crisis; financial problems; poor study techniques; badly structured and boring presentations by lecturers are few of the many factors which cause failure for the students.

In Bangladesh, students and their family give huge emphasis on course selection at university level based on the future job market. Parents and students feel secured if students can enroll into a course which can help them to ensure future job security. Thus, the opportunity of appropriate choice of course at university gives massive advantage to the students. At the same time, students who are not in their choice of course feel enormous pressure and their performance is also hampered.

Another significant factor impacting students' academic performance was regular class attendance and timely examination preparation and assignment submission. Students perceived these factors as crucial for their academic success or failure. As per the finding of this study, for first-year students, self-confidence; self-motivation and self-disciplines are the most important personal traits which determines the success and failure at university level. Writing skill works as a controlling factor for students' to be successful in their university life as written assessment is the main method to evaluate students' academic performance in Bangladesh, Therefore, effective written communications skills was ranked as top-level influencing success factor by the first-year students.

The findings suggests that, teachers' content knowledge, perdagogical knowledge, skills and relation with students also works as controlling factors for student's performance. This finding supports Bamidele and Bamidele (2013) stated that teachers/lectures are key factor for student's success at university level. Kunter *et al.* (2008) [cited in Hien Thu Thi Le et al. (2020)], found that passionate, energetic, animated, inspiring teaching and teachers' presentation style products superior quality learning and student achievements.

In the context of this study, learning surroundings like family support; encouragement, motivation and support from teachers', good accommodation; stable personal life; support from peers; availability of quality learning resources; consistent use of the library resources; adaptability with university procedures and guidelines create a positive impact on students' academic life. Oppositely, inability to cope with stress; failure to approach teachers for help; lack of self-assessment; too many extra unnecessary interests; procrastination; fear of failure; inadequate university library; lack of maturity from the students'; influence of peer group impact academic performance in reverse.

Conclusion

The results of the study provide an important insight into the factors that affects first-year student's academic performance. The results of this study cannot be generalized to other contexts although the results support findings from several earlier studies. Further investigation may be conducted by increasing the respondents' size in order to gain profound understandings into the perceptions and different research methodology may be undertaken to understand the influencing factors for students' academic performance.

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